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The Percentage of Waterproofed Soil in the Italian Regions

On average it grew by 3.03% in the Italian regions between 2015 and 2021

Istat calculates the waterproofing of the soil by artificial cover. The variable is defined as the percentage of waterproofed soil on the total land surface. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2015 and 2021.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage of soil waterproofed in 2021. Lombardy is in first place for the value of soil waterproofing with a value of 12.37 units, followed by Veneto with 11.93 and Campania with 10, 54 units. In the middle of the table is Piedmont with a value of 6.98 units, followed by the Marche with a value of 6.95 units and Sicily with a value of 6.52 units. Basilicata closes the ranking with a value of 3.23 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 3.06 units and Valle D'Aosta with an amount of 2.16 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions for percentage change in waterproofed soil between 2015 and 2021. Liguria is in first place for percentage change in waterproofed soil between 2015 and 2021 with a value equal to 8.74% corresponding to a change from amount of 7.21 units up to 7.84 units. Piedmont follows with a variation equal to 6.40% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.56 units up to a value of 6.98 units. Basilicata is in third place with a variation equal to +3.86% corresponding to a variation between 3.11 units up to 3.23 units. In the middle of the ranking is Veneto with a growth in waterproofed surface with a value equal to 2.49% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.64 units up to 11.93 units. Campania follows with a value of +2.43% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 10.29 units up to a value of 8.95 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a variation equal to +2.29% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 8.75 units up to a value of 8.95 units. Among the last places we have Umbria with a value equal to +1.54% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.20 units up to a value of 5.28 units. Calabria follows with a value of 1.20 units equal to a variation from an amount of 5.02 units up to a value of 5.08 units. Tuscany is in last place with a value equal to +1.15% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.10 units up to a value of 6.17 units. On average, the percentage of waterproofed soil grew by 3.03% between 2015 and 2021 in the Italian regions.

Italian macro regions. The value of the percentage of waterproofed soil grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2015 and 2021. In particular, this value grew by 1.94% in the North-East, by 1.89% in the South, 1.84% in the Islands, 1.71% in the South, 1.66% in the North, 1.51% in the North-West and 1.5% in the Centre. The percentage of sealed soil has grown more in the southern macro-regions

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than in the northern regions, even though the northern regions have higher absolute levels of sealed soil.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Five clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Calabria, Abruzzo, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: Puglia, Lazio, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna;
- Cluster 3: Veneto, Lombardy, Campania;
- Cluster 4: Trentino Alto Adige, Basilicata, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta, Molise;
- Cluster 5: Piedmont, Sicily, Marche, Tuscany, Liguria.

From the point of view of the average, the following ordering of the clusters results: C3>C2>C5>C1>C4. The clustering therefore highlights a very jagged dimension of the condition of the Italian regions in terms of soil waterproofing value. The leading regions are Lombardy, Veneto and Campania. In last place are Trentino Alto Adige, Basilicata, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta and Molise. We can note that the clusters are very heterogeneous from each other in both the geographical, economic and social sense. We can probably see a weak positive relationship between the value of the soil sealing level and the population. Regions that have a higher number of soil seals tend to be characterized by a higher level of population and population density. It is likely that population density and population in an absolute sense are one of the dominant reasons for land consumption. On the contrary, it seems that economic motivations are absolutely irrelevant for the motivation of land consumption. In fact, regions with low per capita income such as Campania and Puglia have very high levels of land consumption comparable, especially in the case of Campania, to regions which have higher per capita income such as Lombardy and Veneto. This condition means that land consumption is generally independent of the value per square meter in euro of the areas subjected to waterproofing.

Conclusions. The value of land consumption grew by 3.03% between 2015 and 2021 on average for the Italian regions. The leading regions for land consumption are Lombardy, Veneto and Campania. Both absolute population level and population density are likely to be variables that predict land use. Considering the Italian macro-regions, it appears that the northern regions tend to have a higher level of land consumption than the southern regions, although this overall effect could be due to the presence of Lombardy and Veneto in the sample of the northern regions. In fact, in 2021 soil waterproofing in Lombardy reached the level of 12.37% while in Veneto it reached 11.93%. Obviously there are many risks in soil waterproofing which refer above all to the growth of hydrogeological risk. For example, the fact that in Liguria the value of soil waterproofing between 2015 and 2021 grew by almost 9% is very serious for the protection of the territory. In fact, Liguria is notoriously one of the most fragile regions from the point of view of hydrogeological risk, with high risks of landslides and landslides. Land consumption is very serious, especially in areas of the country characterized by the presence of rivers, valleys, mountains and hills, i.e. in the vast majority of Italian territory. Institutions need to pay attention to land consumption to ensure that the economic benefits deriving from construction are not lost in the growth of social costs deriving from the growth of hydrogeological risk.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

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